

ANALYSIS OF TEAM TACTICS IMPLEMENTED BY THE GOALKEEPER IN THE FOOTBALL GAME .

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ANNOTATION

Football in his mind of the goalkeeper in success tactical skills big important have The goalkeeper collective tactics within skills protection and in attack own on the contrary finds This skills in defense the team members with good communication do to them support show , returned the balls management , directly and indirectly in blows the wall organize to attack while the ball safe way to the game to put and fast the attack organize reach such as of cases consists of The goalkeeper play during collective to tactics compliance to do his himself and team for success the key will be Therefore , the goalkeeper in training sessions another aspects with one in line collective tactics training is also a place take need This of research the goal of the goalkeeper protection and on the attack collective tactics according to actions is learning .

Keywords : Football , Goalkeeper , Team , Tactics, Techniques, Defense, correct and indirectly blows .

ENTER

Football in his mind of the goalkeeper in success goalkeeper tactics important important have Goalkeeper tactics " football in his mind of the goalkeeper own team and rival of the team all features in consideration received without , to the game effect doer internal and external factors account to the goal according to done increased actions " is defined as This point of view I mean , football in his mind goalkeeper tactics are individual and collective tactics as two type is divided . This in research goalkeeper tactics inside collective tactics analysis to be done goal done

The goalkeeper collective tactics

Modern football in the concept the ball loss in the case of the team each one player protection player is protection principles compliance to do need Other from the side , the team again the ball to the hand when entering , players attack principles act accordingly it is necessary The goalkeeper is also this protection and attack principles except it's not .

Quality goalkeepers the ball right way to the game to put ability have to be and each trip the ball to the game in putting attack start for the ball from where and when to the game to put they know need This point of view meaning , the goalkeeper the ball while driving him hand with or leg with to the game to put the team for useful to be solution to do it is necessary The ball hand or leg with to the game when putting , the goalkeeper without pressure to the players or own the team of members the ball take over possible has been to places transmission need

The goalkeeper collective tactics protection and attack according to two in the direction seeing output can

In defense collective tactics

Goalkeeper of the team protection in his mind the most last is a player . It is protection line i with one acting as a whole , the opponent goal hit prevention takes Protection o' players of the opponent attack to stop succeeded didn't happen in cases , last task to the goalkeeper is loaded .

Goalkeeper only protect last man not but communication and support through own protection of the players indispensable one part is considered Below of the goalkeeper in defense to show possible has been tactical actions given .

COMMUNICATION

Communication football in the team efficiency indicator as the most important of factors is one Football of the team communication quality usually the team individual indicators of members with directly depends . Therefore , the team o' players for efficient communication to do is a necessity . If one of the team good compatibility to be provided If so , the players mutually ease with communication do it to get need Communication only message to send not but coming also receive messages do it to receive means This point of view by implication , communication of the goalkeeper important qualities one is considered Goalkeeper protection o' players with good communication when installed , of the team protection better organize will be done and to the opponent goal hit possibilities less will be

The goalkeeper the most behind located , to him the game the most wide from the corner observation enable gives If the goalkeeper protection to the players in time necessary warnings giving if so , of the team protection efficiency in improvement big help gives Also a goalkeeper attack during back go to the defense near was not friends their to be need has been positions warning , watcher as very important role plays

Play during of the goalkeeper in front of playable one part there is . The goalkeeper of duties one , the team to members behind them what are that is happening and their where location about message is to give Goalkeeper to the situation depending on the ball output or the ball in distancing protection to the player help to give need Goalkeeper protection o' players with communication to 5 principles when doing compliance to do must :

1. Information sure to be to be surprised that puts data not given it is necessary
2. Information short and in lo to be need Too much p information to give time not to be can
3. Information while being given calm down to be and sound tone is normal keep need
4. Panic reason to be possible has been wrong warnings does not give need
5. Information while giving strictly and command giver to be need

Above telling passed to the points based on the goalkeeper the team to a friend who sends messages five main to the chapter separate can :

1. Ball p on the left when played , the goalkeeper right on the side opponents control to do in order to right side good watch and protect back is about to pass has been to the opponent against friends warns .

2. Your opponent fine area around in case , the opponent by blow to give being prepared balls for the most near a friend warns .

3. Play passing towards looked at protection friends back on the side what are that is happening according to they can't . In such cases of friends right decision acceptance to do for necessary warnings gives

4. Own protection players with one different when trying to hit the ball friends warn the ball themselves take to get possible ("I do it " I will " loudly in voice) means . Necessity at birth acts early .

5. Ball p from protection removed in the case of friends quickly forward out , the opponent offside catches and numerically in attack to advantage achieve for them warns .

Support

The goalkeeper support distance, engaged behind is located protection player with his between is the distance. If this distance very big if so, the opponent players protect back the ball empty from the field their uses can

In particular, this empty field most of the time of the goalkeeper own the team players rival of the team fine to the field near in the place goal position create for pressure while conducting appear will be Throw the ball away loss as a result surface coming possible has been in counter-acts, this empty to the field the ball from falling before rival from the player before to the ball ownership to do for goalkeeper awake to be, from the opponent before to the ball output and goal position not to create for the ball distance need

If protection of players fine area in front of is located if so, the goalkeeper's to be need has been place gate front line of the field around will be If protection of players medium field around if so, the goalkeeper's to be need has been place fine front line of the field around will be

Return the ball

Return the ball the rule of the goalkeeper in nature no has been one action is considered Because only head and blue crack with given from passes except, how return the ball goalkeeper into his hand take possible it's not. That's why for goalkeeper each both from the foot using, quickly short and long the blows perform opportunity have to be it is necessary

Team of members goalkeeper for gave return balls never when dangerous not to be and the goalkeeper difficult to the situation not put need Necessary cases given return balls gate from the area out, to the edges direction it is necessary

That's right and indirectly in blows the wall

Teams free in blows goal hit for different tactics of changes try they see This from blows of the goalkeeper position with one in line, of is set the importance of the wall as well big On the wall to be need has been players earlier in training to be determined and the wall the captain determination necessary Wall option as long as long tall from the players organize to be done need and blow to give of place to the gate the distance and proximity looking players the number to be determined it is necessary To the gate opposite and fine area from around being given 4-6 people in shots the wall installation need Reverse falsies for and directly from the direction one person the wall out output benefit to bring can

25-30 meters to the gate in the distance to be given in blows wall 2-3 people with installation can From the side to be given in blows while wall 1 or 2 people with installation need Very little in cases, 9 meters to the gate in the distance indirectly in blows all the team of players gate to the line will be located. The goalkeeper is also this of the wall in front of will be Goalkeeper the wall to the captain coordination giving, close direct level the wall installs Goalkeeper of the wall location and to the wall entering the players oral and oral not (hand hints with) communication through determines Wall players leg to the fingers rise advantage gives Wall players in the middle space not to leave need Of these all of them goalkeeper observation and necessity at birth necessary warnings to give it is necessary

of the dam last place and another direct between distance of the goalkeeper the first next responsibility area is considered Goalkeeper barrage over shoot possible was to the balls against very caution to be need These are the goalkeepers for difficult rescue to be maybe, but reaction speed and speed good has been goalkeepers such cases to success they achieve

On the attack collective tactics

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Goalkeeper protection game winner as if you look at it , the team to attack in passing attack player as duties there is .

Ball p at the goalkeeper attack when starter the first player is considered Therefore , the goalkeeper the ball to manage when , it is short time inside the field out of sight forgiveness and the most suitable a friend to determine necessary The ball to the game while putting , his in front of two selection will be : first , the ball hand with protection or medium field to the players giving , safe one the attack start possible ; secondly , the leg with (true or indirectly blow , out blow or degage through) forward handing over and countertact start can

Safe The attack Start

Here tactical the goal , the ball Turn and rest and reliable the attack done is to increase . Goalkeeper the ball after catching , on defense the team friends free to the place out , opponent of the players from absence used without the ball they ask .

Quick Attack Start

The goalkeeper control past the ball fast and sure way to the game putting , of the team fast to attack to pass possibility gives In particular , the opponent of the team pressure as a result rival in defense from time to time with empty sh places appear will be This empty sh to the place of the goalkeeper sure the ball transmission with entering player rival the team unbalanced without catches and so , a goal hit position access opportunity to the hand enters

Summary

Goalkeeper football of the team indispensable one is part of He is himself the team players with together in defense and in attack important tasks performs If the opponent by never how pressure if not , the goalkeeper fine in the field blows own protection players with by passing done to increase need , as well as the ball forward release through time and distance saves . Goalkeeper football in his mind important role to play for own team and rival of the players actions understand and accordingly tactical actions determine necessary If the goalkeeper protection tactics good do it if he knows , this goal not to transfer help to give can If the attack tactics are also successful if he does , his team for goal hit opportunity to create can So the goalkeeper collective tactics practices good perform of the team in success important role plays

The goalkeeper safe attack start his is the task . The ball to the game sure way to put necessary Not clear blows rival to the team counterattack opportunity gives Also , his of the team balance break can If the team one term pressure under If so , the goalkeeper of friends installed places spreading for the game a little slow down can

Goalkeeper ball , exceptions account if , it is empty own protection to the players pass it to the game in putting useful will be Right from the side coming rival in the attack goalkeeper to the ball have when (pressure if not) the ball to the game from the left side , from the left side attack when it comes while right from the side to put to the goal according to will be

USED LITERATURE .

1.Yarasheva Dilnoza,(2024). BODY HYDRATION OF FEMALE HANDBALL PLAYERS DURING THE GAME STATUS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 4(04), 07–14. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume04Issue04-02>

2.Dilnoza, Y. (2024). MASHG'ULOT JARAYONIDA GANDBOLCHINING FUNKSIONAL HOLATINI O'RGANISH. *PEDAGOG*, 7(6), 39-46.

3. Yarasheva, D. (2024). GANDBOLDA TO'PNI QO'LLASH TEXNIKALARI. *PEDAGOG*, 7(5), 13-20.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

4. Yarasheva, D. (2024). TYPES AND EFFECTIVENESS OF FITNESS TRAINING. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 299-307.
5. Yarasheva, D. (2024). IN HANDBALL GYMS: SAFE PHYSICAL EXERCISES AND INJURY PREVENTION. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 23-32.
6. Yarasheva, D. (2024). USE OF HANDBALL INDUSTRY AND TECHNOLOGY. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 9-15.
7. Yarasheva, D. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF ENDURANCE IN HANDBALL. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 4(3), 73-77.
8. Dilnoza, Y. (2023). GANDBOL MURABBIYLARINING FIKRIGA KO'RA, SPORTCHILARNING KORSATKICHLARIGA PSIXOLOGIK TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR. *Research and Publications*, 1(1), 86-100.
9. Yarasheva, D. (2024). INVESTIGATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOME PARAMETERS OF PHYSICAL TRAINING IN ELITE HANDBALL PLAYERS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 696-701. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/31182>
10. Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Physical education lessons in the process of unumpedagogik methods. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 345-354.
11. Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Physical downloads and the rest of fulfilling exercise mutual dependence. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 394-409.
12. Ayubovna, S. M. (2024). Principles and models of physical education. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(3), 149-156.
13. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Physical attributes (capabilities) of development of the main legality. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 373-380. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/rjtds/article/view/1712>
14. Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Jismoniy tarbiyaning vositalariga va jismoniy mashqlar xarakteristikasi. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 370-378.
15. Ayubovna, S. M. (2024). Gimnastikaning-ta'limni rivojlantiruvchi turlari." XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" Nomli Respublika Ilmiy-Amaliy Konferensiyasi, 2(1), 100-107.
16. Ayubovna, S. M. (2024). Gimnastika sport turining turlari va tasniflashi." XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 2(1), 108-115.
17. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). The pedagogical category of physical exercise. Spatial exercises. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 509-518. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/rjtds/article/view/1774>
18. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). SPORT, ESTETIKA VA ESTETIK TARBIYA. *Oriental Journal of Academic and Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(3), 82-89. <http://inno-world.uz/index.php/ojamr/article/view/68>
19. Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Harakat malakalarini shakllantirishning fiziologik asoslari va sport texnikasini o'rgatish. *E'tiqod va madaniyatning kesishgan joylari: Amerika diniy va madaniyat tadqiqotlari jurnali (2993-2599)*, 1(9), 87-94.
20. Azamat Orunbayev, (2023) NONUSHTANING MASHQ BAJARISHGA TA'SIRI. *International journal of scientific researchers* 2(2), 3-6.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-2

21. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). USING TECHNOLOGY IN A SPORTS ENVIRONMENT. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 39–49. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-07>
22. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). FITNES VA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA MURABBIYLIK YO'NALISHIGA KONTSEPTUAL YONDASHUV. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(8), 23–28. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/431>
23. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). PANDEMIYA DAVRIDA MOBIL SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH VA FITNES DASTURLARI (PROGRAM). *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(7), 37–42. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/414>
24. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). APPROACHES, BEHAVIORAL CHARACTERISTICS, PRINCIPLES AND METHODS OF WORK OF COACHES AND MANAGERS IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 133–151. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-16>
25. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). GLOBALIZATION AND SPORTS INDUSTRY. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 164–182. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-18>
26. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). SOCIAL SPORTS MARKETING. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 121–134. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-17>
27. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). RECOVERY STRATEGY IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 135–147. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-18>